

Does distributing non-interactive teaching contribute to learning? Students' academic self-concept and work ethic matter[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Explaining learning contents to a fictitious peer (i.e., non-interactive teaching) improves learning, yet this effect is modest, heterogeneous, and likely influenced by individual differences. We examined whether the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching could be increased by incorporating drawing or distributing teaching. We realized a 3×2 field experimental design ($N = 317$), crossing the factors learning activity (restudy, teaching-only, teaching + drawing) and timing (after the study phase or distributed three times throughout the study phase). Overall, teaching resulted in better immediate conceptual knowledge than restudying, mediated by the level of completeness. This teaching effect was most pronounced in the after-study condition. However, drawing did not enhance conceptual knowledge. Students who taught underestimated their immediate knowledge. No lasting effects were observed. Students with higher academic self-concept or work ethic benefited more from teaching, highlighting the moderating role of inter-individual differences for instructional interventions.

Educational relevance and implications statement: This classroom study demonstrates that non-interactive teaching is an effective instructional method in secondary school physics education. The findings highlight the importance of considering students' individual differences, such as academic self-concept or work ethic, when designing such learning activities. These insights emphasize the need for adapted and differentiated approaches that can better account for individual differences, ensuring that non-interactive teaching can be effective across diverse student populations.

1. Introduction

Learning by teaching is widely recognized as an effective way to enhance learning (Fiorella & Mayer, 2016; Pi et al., 2021). Recently, it has been shown that teaching previously learned contents even to a fictitious non-present peer (cf. non-interactive teaching), is a powerful generative activity (Fiorella & Mayer, 2013; Hoogerheide et al., 2014; Lachner et al., 2022). Non-interactive teaching may help students construct a meaningful mental representation of the learning contents, contributing to learning and metacomprehension (Fiorella, 2023; Fiorella & Mayer, 2016; Wittrock, 1989). However, previous research

indicated that the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching is relatively modest (Kobayashi, 2024; Lachner et al., 2021) and that there is large heterogeneity among the findings (Hoogerheide, Visee, et al., 2019; Jacob et al., 2022). These findings suggest that the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching may depend on students' prerequisites (e.g., Jacob et al., 2022) and that optimizing its potential may require modifications, such as combining it with other strategies.

To address these gaps, we conducted an authentic classroom experiment with secondary physics students in the context of inquiry learning to investigate whether the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching can be improved by 1) adding drawing as a visual-spatial generative activity

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to the act of verbal teaching (cf. drawing-facilitates-explaining hypothesis, [Fiorella, 2023](#)), and by 2) distributing the generative activity across the study phase, as a concurrent activity ([Bisra et al., 2018](#); [Cuddy & Jacoby, 1982](#); [Lachner et al., 2020](#)). Additionally, we explored whether inter-individual differences might be associated with the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching.

2. Learning by non-interactive teaching

An effective way to enhance student learning is to have them teach the previously learned contents to others, a method known as *learning by teaching* ([Fiorella & Mayer, 2016](#); [Pi et al., 2021](#)). Recently, researchers have begun to explore how learning by teaching can be effective even in non-interactive contexts. This so-called *non-interactive teaching* is a generative learning activity in which students are asked to generate an explanation to a fictitious peer of the previously learned contents ([Lachner et al., 2022](#)). Grounded in Wittrock's generative model of learning (1989, 2010), and related models such as the select-organize-integrate (SOI) model of generative learning ([Fiorella & Mayer, 2016](#)), non-interactive teaching aims at fostering students' meaningful learning by triggering active knowledge construction processes ([Brod, 2021](#); [Fiorella, 2023](#); [Fiorella & Mayer, 2016](#)). During teaching, students engage in generative processes which are regarded as enhancing learning and metacomprehension. First, students need to select the most relevant information of the learning contents. Second, they need to organize the information into a coherent order to be able to generate a comprehensible explanation. Third, the students need to integrate the new information with their prior knowledge to be able to provide further details and examples that go beyond the given materials to address their explanation to the audience's needs. Throughout this process, non-interactive teaching may trigger metacomprehension to monitor one's own understanding. Importantly, even the mere expectancy to teach—without actually teaching—can contribute to students' learning by encouraging deeper processing and knowledge organization ([Fiorella & Mayer, 2013, 2014](#); [Guerrero & Wiley, 2021](#); [Hoogerheide et al., 2014](#)).

Several studies demonstrated beneficial effects of non-interactive teaching regarding students' learning and metacomprehension ([Hoogerheide, Renkl, et al., 2019](#); [Jacob et al., 2020](#); [Lachner et al., 2021](#); [Pi et al., 2021](#)). Recent meta-analytical evidence showed small positive effects of non-interactive teaching regarding students' cognitive learning ([Kobayashi, 2024](#): $g = 0.27$, small effect; [Lachner et al., 2021](#): $g = 0.22$ for conceptual knowledge, $g = 0.16$ for transfer, both small effects; [Ribosa & Duran, 2022](#): $g = 0.17$, small effect). Similarly, researchers found positive effects on metacomprehension ([Fukaya, 2013](#); [Jacob et al., 2020](#); [Lachner et al., 2020](#)). [Fukaya \(2013\)](#), for instance, conducted an experiment in which university students were asked to read five texts with the intention to teach the contents afterwards. Then, students either taught the contents (teaching condition) or only planned to teach but did not generate an explanation (intention-only condition). The control group had the intention of writing keywords after reading the text and then actually wrote keywords. Results showed that students who taught demonstrated significantly better monitoring accuracy, meaning that they judged their knowledge in the test more accurately than those who only intended to teach or those who wrote keywords (main effect: $\eta^2 = 0.17$, large effect).

Notably, prior research predominantly took place in laboratory settings with university students with only immediate or short delay posttests (e.g., [Fiorella & Mayer, 2013, 2014](#); [Hoogerheide et al., 2014](#)). Because laboratory settings might differ from authentic classrooms in terms of their study populations and contextual factors like more pronounced learner diversity, environmental distractions and social dynamics (e.g., [Dinsmore & Alexander, 2012](#)), it is unclear whether non-interactive teaching is also effective in authentic classrooms with school students (see also [Sibley et al., 2024](#)). Additionally, little is known about potential lasting learning effects of non-interactive

teaching, as prior research predominantly focused on effects of teaching regarding students' immediate learning and not their lasting learning.

2.1. Enhancing the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching

Even though the potential benefits of non-interactive teaching have been documented by recent meta-analyses ([Kobayashi, 2024](#); [Lachner et al., 2021](#); [Ribosa & Duran, 2022](#)), their findings varied considerably among and even within studies. While some reported positive effects, others found null or even negative effects, indicating that non-interactive teaching is not necessarily effective. Recently, researchers have begun to explore two primary strategies for enhancing non-interactive teaching. First, they have combined non-interactive teaching with additional generative learning activities like drawing (e.g., [Fiorella & Kuhlmann, 2020](#)). Second, they have investigated ways to improve the activity of non-interactive teaching (e.g., [Lachner & Neuburg, 2019](#)), such as optimizing the timing of the learning activities (i.e., distribution, see [Lachner et al., 2020](#)).

2.1.1. Enhancing non-interactive teaching with drawing

Drawing is regarded as a learning activity in which students are asked to draw the previously learned contents ([Fiorella & Mayer, 2016](#)). During drawing, students need to re-organize the information to be able to generate visual-spatial representations, which often surpassed the initially provided information and therefore can enhance students' learning and metacomprehension ([Ainsworth & Scheiter, 2021](#); [Fiorella, 2023](#); [Van Meter & Firetto, 2013](#)). Regarding students' learning, [Fiorella and Zhang's \(2018\)](#) demonstrated in their meta-analysis that students benefited more from drawing than from reading or text-focused strategies such as summarizing or paraphrasing ($d = 0.46$ for comprehension, small effect; $d = 0.70$ for transfer, medium effect). Regarding students' metacomprehension, [Fiorella and Jaeger \(2023\)](#), for instance, showed that students who either created their own visualizations or used those generated by instructors exhibited better monitoring accuracy than those who studied with only text or provided visuals (for explain judgments: $d = 0.36$, small effect).

According to the generative sense-making framework proposed by [Fiorella \(2023\)](#), non-interactive teaching emphasizes generating coherent verbal explanations, which supports knowledge generalization. In contrast, drawing emphasizes creating an external visualization ([Cox, 1999](#); [Schmidgall et al., 2019](#); [Van Meter & Firetto, 2013](#)) that organizes information in a conceptually meaningful way. Non-interactive teaching and drawing place considerable demands on working memory when generating explanations and drawings, while drawing also enables students to offload and externalize their thoughts through visual representation, thereby possibly freeing up cognitive resources that students could invest in learning-relevant processes ([Fiorella, 2023](#); [Fiorella & Mayer, 2016](#); [Sweller et al., 2011](#)). [Fiorella \(2023\)](#) further suggested that combining these approaches can be particularly effective: the visualizing function of drawing can scaffold and strengthen the verbal explanation process, providing an external structure that aids in explanation and promotes deeper cognitive and metacognitive engagement.

To date, there is limited research regarding combining teaching and drawing. As an exception, [Fiorella and Kuhlmann \(2020\)](#) examined the influence of drawing and teaching with 120 college students who either taught previously learned contents, created drawings, taught and drew, or restudied the contents. Results of a one-week delayed posttest showed that drawing enhanced students' learning compared to restudying ($d = 1.06$, large effect), which was also true for teaching-only ($d = 0.80$, medium effect) and for combined teaching and drawing compared to restudying ($d = 1.46$, large effect). Moreover, students who taught and drew outperformed students in the drawing-only ($d = 0.65$, medium effect) and teaching-only condition ($d = 0.99$, large effect). Whether these findings can be transferred into authentic classrooms settings with

school students is, however, still an open question.

2.1.2. Enhancing non-interactive teaching through distribution

The timing of teaching may also be critical for the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching. Inspired by approaches of interpolated testing (Pan et al., 2024), distributing a teaching activity within a study session can be more effective than a single teaching activity at the end of a study phase, since multiple generative activity phases may involve multiple chances of generation processes that may contribute to the (re-)construction of knowledge (Cuddy & Jacoby, 1982; for meta-analytical evidence, see Prinz et al., 2020; for related evidence, see Carpenter et al., 2012; Ebersbach et al., 2022). From a metacognitive perspective, distributed learning activities may additionally aid monitoring the learning process and subsequent regulation activities by providing students with multiple opportunities to evaluate their progress, compare their understanding across phases, and adjust their strategies. For example, they can refine time management, prioritize contents, or address misunderstandings, which may improve their monitoring accuracy and learning regulation (Lachner et al., 2020; Schleinschok et al., 2017).

When distributed teaching is effective, it typically involves distributing explanations across multiple learning episodes, allowing students to revisit and reconstruct their knowledge over time. Cuddy and Jacoby (1982, Exp.1) demonstrated this effect in an experiment in which 18 university students learned word pairs, with the second word presented either intact or with missing letters (e.g., TREE: BR-CH), and recalled them after varying intervals. The authors manipulated the number of intervening tasks between repetitions, showing that recall performance improved when prior knowledge was less readily accessible due to a greater number of intervening tasks ($F(2,34) = 5.65, p < .050$). Specifically, recall was higher when four or eight unrelated items appeared between repetitions compared to immediate repetition, but this effect occurred only when students had to reconstruct the missing letters (main effect of repetition condition: $F(1,17) = 16.28, p < .050$; interaction distributing \times repetition: $F(2,34) = 64.71, p < .050$). These findings suggest that distributing learning opportunities, combined with constructive learning processes, can facilitate deeper encoding and stronger memory retention.

However, most of the previous research on teaching and drawing, as well as educational practice, asked students to only teach or draw once, namely at the end of a study phase (Lachner et al., 2020). Thus, little is known about the effect of distributing non-interactive teaching. So far, Lachner et al. (2020) have been the only researchers to systematically distribute the teaching activity within their study. In two experiments, the authors investigated whether distributing non-interactive teaching at one point of time during students' studying (i.e., distributed teaching) would support learning more than non-interactive teaching after the entire study phase (i.e., no distributed teaching). The findings showed that students who taught once during studying achieved higher conceptual knowledge scores in an immediate knowledge test than those who taught once after the study phase ($\eta_p^2 = 0.06$, medium effect). The benefits of distributed teaching were explained by students' more frequent engagement in monitoring.

Although this study provides first evidence that distributing non-interactive teaching matters, it is still unclear whether distributing non-interactive teaching in several phases is even more beneficial, whether the effects of distributed teaching are transferable to classrooms, and whether they also may result in lasting learning effects, since the authors did not apply a delayed posttest.

2.2. Influence of students' individual differences

Against the backdrop of the mixed findings of non-interactive teaching, in their theoretical review, Lachner et al. (2022) advocated for a thorough examination of boundary conditions of non-interactive

teaching, particularly regarding students' prerequisites. Snow's Aptitude-Treatment-Interaction (ATI) theory (1991) provides a framework for understanding how individual differences can influence the effectiveness of instructional strategies. According to the ATI theory (Snow, 1991), the success of an instructional method, such as non-interactive teaching, depends on the alignment between the instructional approach and students' individual aptitudes. Specifically, students' prerequisites—such as prior knowledge, motivational or personality factors—can determine how effectively they engage in and benefit from generative learning activities. These individual differences may affect students' ability to select, organize and integrate new information with existing knowledge—generative processes required for effective learning (Fiorella, 2023; Fiorella & Mayer, 2016).

For instance, prior knowledge is a crucial cognitive factor (Kalyuga, 2007; McNamara et al., 1996; Richter et al., 2018) that influences how students construct robust mental representations and efficiently integrate new information (Lachner et al., 2021; Mayer, 2009). The ability to form these connections is essential for meaningful learning (Fiorella, 2023; Fiorella & Mayer, 2016). Students with limited prior knowledge may struggle to make these connections (Renkl, 2014), often resulting in suboptimal learning outcomes (Roelle & Nückles, 2019). In contrast, students with high prior knowledge may find generative learning strategies redundant, as they can manage learning more independently (Castro-Alonso et al., 2021). Thus, generative learning strategies, such as non-interactive teaching, may be particularly beneficial for students with lower prior knowledge, as they provide needed support (McNamara & Scott, 1999).

To date, only Hoogerheide, Renkl, et al. (2019) examined the influence of university students' prior knowledge regarding generative learning within non-interactive teaching settings. In their study, the researchers compared the performance of students engaged in teaching activities with those engaged in restudying, within the context of electrical troubleshooting tasks. Findings indicated that the teaching condition outperformed the restudy condition on both isomorphic ($\eta_p^2 = 0.07$, medium effect) and transfer problems ($\eta_p^2 = 0.07$, medium effect) in posttest performance. Regarding transfer, students with lower prior knowledge particularly benefited from teaching, while the teaching condition eliminated the positive relationship between prior knowledge and transfer performance observed in the restudy condition ($\beta = 0.56$, medium effect in the restudy control group).

Relatedly, prior research has highlighted academic self-concept as a fundamental prerequisite for learning. Academic self-concept describes how students perceive and evaluate their own competency within a particular academic field (Marsh et al., 2017; Shavelson et al., 1976). It is influenced by various factors, including experiences, feedback from teachers, and social comparisons. These comparisons are crucial in shaping students' beliefs about their academic competence, as they continuously assess their performance relative to that of their classmates or peers within the learning context (Marsh et al., 2008). Although academic self-concept has been shown to be positively correlated with learning outcomes (Möller et al., 2020; Valentine et al., 2004), its role in non-interactive teaching contexts remains underexplored. Given that academic self-concept influences how students approach and engage with learning tasks (Urhahne & Wijnia, 2023), understanding its interaction with instructional strategies like learning by teaching is critical. As an exception, Jacob et al. (2022) examined non-interactive teaching with seventh-grade school students who either taught the learning contents to a fictitious peer or were engaged in a retrieval practice. Results showed no effects among conditions. Interestingly, explorative analyses revealed that students with low academic self-concept benefited from teaching, possibly because they gained more from structured, generative activities like teaching. In contrast, students with high academic self-concept appeared to benefit more from retrieval practice, as they likely did not require additional scaffolding or structured learning activities to achieve optimal learning outcomes

(interaction effect: $\beta = 0.49$, medium effect).

In addition to cognitive (i.e., prior knowledge) and motivational (i.e., academic self-concept) influencing factors, research also highlighted students' conscientiousness as a crucial individual pre-requisite for learning (Komaraju et al., 2009; Poropat, 2009; Richardson et al., 2012; Waldeyer et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023). Conscientiousness includes self-control, responsibility, diligence, goal-directed behavior, effective planning, orderliness, delay gratification, and adherence to rules and norms (De Fruyt et al., 2008; John et al., 2008; John & Srivastava, 1999; McCrae & John, 1992; Roberts et al., 2014). There is ongoing debate about whether conscientiousness functions as a general trait or has domain-specific expressions (Mammadov, 2022; Meyer et al., 2023). Conscientiousness can also be operationalized in different ways, one of which is work ethic as a facet of this trait (Roberts et al., 2014; see also De Fruyt et al., 2008; Mang et al., 2018). Work ethic refers to the propensity for persistence, diligence, and hard work in goal-oriented tasks (Roberts et al., 2014). A strong work ethic could positively influence students' engagement in generative learning activities, as it may affect how thoroughly, precisely, and consistently students approach these tasks. According to the generative sense-making framework (Fiorella, 2023), these behaviors can facilitate generative processes, for instance, students with higher levels of work ethic may be more likely to invest effort in thoroughly understanding new material and connecting it with prior knowledge. These qualities are particularly important in non-interactive teaching contexts, where students must independently regulate their learning behaviors. Therefore, a strong work ethic may enhance the effectiveness of generative learning strategies and contribute to improved learning outcomes and metacomprehension (e.g., Song et al., 2020 for related empirical evidence; Spielmann et al., 2022 for a comprehensive review). However, to our knowledge, no one has taken students' work ethic into account when analyzing non-interactive teaching.

3. The present study

In this study, we combined non-interactive teaching with drawing and varied its interpolation (after-study activity versus distributed throughout the study phase). Additionally, we explored students' individual differences (i.e., prior knowledge, academic self-concept, work ethic) as crucial moderating factors of non-interactive teaching. We tested the following preregistered hypotheses (https://aspredicted.org/RM1_1TF):

3.1. Generation hypothesis (H1)

Based on the generative learning theory (Fiorella, 2023; Fiorella & Mayer, 2016; Wittrock, 1989, 2010), we hypothesized that students who engage in non-interactive teaching (teaching-only, teaching + drawing) show better performance than students who restudy the learning contents (restudy control group) regarding their a) conceptual knowledge (Fiorella & Mayer, 2013, 2014; Hoogerheide, Visee, et al., 2019) and b) monitoring accuracy (Fukaya, 2013; Jacob et al., 2020). Additionally, we explored whether the effects also resulted in lasting learning (delayed test after eight weeks).

3.2. Drawing hypothesis (H2)

Previous studies highlighted the benefit of learner-generated visualizations (Cooper et al., 2017) and combining teaching and drawing for knowledge enhancement (Fiorella, 2023; Fiorella & Kuhlmann, 2020). Accordingly, we hypothesized that students who teach and draw (teaching + drawing) outperform students who only teach the new contents (teaching-only) regarding their a) conceptual knowledge and b) monitoring accuracy. Additionally, we explored whether the effects also resulted in lasting learning (delayed test after eight weeks).

3.3. Distribution hypothesis (H3)

Previous research showed that distributed learning activities can be more effective than learning activities after a study phase (Lachner et al., 2020). Therefore, we hypothesized that students in the distributed conditions would outperform students in the after-study conditions regarding their a) conceptual knowledge, and b) monitoring accuracy. Additionally, we explored whether the effects also resulted in lasting learning (delayed test after eight weeks). Furthermore, we explored potential interaction effects between the learning activity (i.e., restudy, teaching-only, teaching + drawing) and the timing factor (i.e., after-study, distributing).

3.4. Explorative analyses on students' individual differences

Following Lachner et al. (2022), we closely inspected students' individual differences, as they could critically influence their learning and metacomprehension (Hoogerheide, Renkl, et al., 2019; Jacob et al., 2022; Song et al., 2020). To replicate previous findings, we included students' prior knowledge (Hoogerheide, Renkl, et al., 2019) and academic self-concept (Jacob et al., 2022). As an extension, we included students' work ethic as a facet of conscientiousness, given its crucial role as a predictor of learning as evidenced by related research (Bareis et al., 2024; Song et al., 2020; Spielmann et al., 2022).

4. Method

4.1. Participants and design

In total, 345 school students in the seventh and eighth grade from four secondary schools in south-west Germany participated in our study. As some school students ($n = 28$) only attended the pretest or the delayed test but were absent in the main part of the study (i.e., teaching unit), we excluded these data sets from the subsequent analyses, resulting in a total sample size of $N = 317$ (for more details see Appendix A). This sample size exceeded the required sample size of 206 students, computed via an a-priori power analysis using G*Power ($f = 0.25$, $\alpha = 0.05$, $1 - \beta = 0.90$, ANCOVA with one covariate – prior conceptual knowledge or prior monitoring accuracy).¹

The mean age of the final sample was 12.37 years ($SD = 0.70$) and 49.50 % were female. Most of the students (60.47 %) stated that German was their native language, 14.29 % grew up bilingual with German, and 25.25 % had another native language. The students showed relatively low prior cognitive knowledge ($M = 7.80$, $SD = 3.6$; max. 30 points), and moderately high levels of academic self-concept ($M = 2.75$, $SD = 0.56$) and work ethic ($M = 2.96$, $SD = 0.50$) in physics, as measured on Likert scales from one to four.

To test our hypotheses, we applied a 3×2 design with learning activity (restudy, teaching-only, teaching + drawing) and timing (after-study, distributed) as between-subject factors. Thus, students were either engaged in the learning activity only once, namely after the study phase (after-study: restudy: $n = 53$, teaching-only: $n = 52$, teaching + drawing: $n = 53$) or several times during the study phase (distributed: restudy: $n = 48$, teaching-only: $n = 56$, teaching + drawing: $n = 55$). The learning tasks were realized as open-book activities, allowing students access to the learning material. We implemented restudy as control condition, since restudy induces generative processes to a less pronounced extent (Fiorella & Mayer, 2016).

¹ We based our power analysis on ANCOVA rather than planned contrasts to adopt a more conservative approach. As our analyses used multilevel modeling, power considerations should be interpreted with caution.

Fig. 1. Students' Experimental Setup on the Converging Lens and its Images.

4.2. The teaching unit

The curriculum-aligned teaching unit in physics was about the converging lens and its images (geometrical optics), a standard topic for this age group. The teaching unit was taught by a certified physics teacher with 10 years of teaching experience (first author) who was also the researcher at the schools. All instructional resources used (i.e., introduction, overview sheet, experimentation worksheet) were based on Flegr et al. (2023).

4.2.1. Introduction to the converging lens

The introduction to the converging lens and its basic functions was delivered through a teacher-led presentation using visual slides. The presentation covered the use of lenses in daily life, prompting students to connect with their prior knowledge through questions such as "Where can you find lenses in your everyday life?", followed by a class discussion and examination of visual examples. Additionally, the introduction also provided a definition of converging lenses, key terms, and an explanation with an illustration of light refraction through a converging lens, along with basic details on the images formed by these lenses. An additional overview sheet outlined the fundamental concepts and functions of converging lenses (see first worksheet by Flegr et al., 2023).

4.2.2. Students' experiments

After the introduction, students examined how covering parts of a converging lens (affecting its diameter) and altering the distance between the object and the lens influenced the resulting image. During these experiments, students utilized an optical bench, an LED lamp with a "Perl-L" aperture, a converging lens, and a white screen. The light source gives a lighting "L"-shaped object, which could be moved closer to or further from the lens. The light from the "L"-shaped object refracts through the lens and forms an inverted image on a movable screen located opposite the lens (Fig. 1).

A worksheet prompted the students to formulate hypotheses (e.g., "What do you think happens to the image of the object when the lens is partially covered?"), answer multiple-choice questions (e.g., "Is the complete 'L' still imaged when the lens is half covered? Yes, there is no difference. / Yes, but the 'L' on the screen is not as bright as before. / No, the 'L' is cut off. / No, the 'L' is no longer visible"), and answer an open-ended question ("Can you explain why that is?"). It also included a table for documenting observations (object distance, image distance, image characteristics), an exercise to select correct word elements (e.g., "If the lens is partly covered, an image of the complete object is still formed / is not formed on the screen"), and a section for comparing initial hypotheses with actual results (e.g., "Compare the mnemonic with your previously formulated hypothesis 1. Was your assumption different than the result? Yes, completely different. / A bit. / No, it was the same").

4.3. Learning activity

During the learning activity, students were asked to either teach the contents to a fictitious peer, to teach and draw a picture, or to restudy the contents. We focused on two main learning objectives of the study (covering parts of a converging lens and altering the distance between the object and the lens) which we addressed in the instructions. Students in the teaching conditions (teaching-only, teaching + drawing) were given the following instruction:

In a message, the student Mia wrote to you two assumptions about the converging lens and its images. Reply to Mia by creating a clear and detailed voice message to Mia so that she can understand the contents without any additional information. Respond to Mia's assumptions. You are allowed to use the materials of the topic, but it is very important that you DO NOT read from them when recording the voice message but formulate it in your own words and incorporate your own thoughts.² You have a total of 15 min to complete this task. Be sure to use all the time.

Students in the teaching-only condition then saw a mock-up chat on a tablet device with the fictitious peer Mia (see Fig. 2, left side) in which Mia stated two assumptions ("I actually believe: When the lens is covered half, only half of the L is shown as an image."; "I actually believe: When I move the object towards the lens, I also have to move the screen closer to the lens in order to see a sharp image on the screen"), addressing common misconceptions about image formation with converging lenses (see Wörner et al., 2022). Students could teach Mia the contents by sending her a voice message.

Students in the teaching + drawing condition received the same text from Mia on a tablet device and could also teach by sending a voice message. In addition, they were provided with two template pictures in which they could draw during teaching (see Fig. 2, right side).

To guarantee that students in the control group were provided with the same contents, we presented them with the following detailed instruction, in which also both main misconceptions were addressed:

Restudy the contents of today's physics lessons. To do this, use today's physics materials: You have received an overview sheet on the basics about the converging lens and its images and you have the instructions and results of the experiments. Use the materials for restudying. Focus on the following two points: What happens to the image if the lens is partially covered? What happens to the image if the distance between the object and the lens is changed? Take notes on this sheet. You may use the front and back of the sheet for this. You have a total of 15 min to complete this task. Be sure to use all the time.

² Note that we checked students' adherence to these instructions and found no indications that students read directly from the materials instead of using their own words. Regarding students' drawings, no visualizations were provided that they could directly replicate.

Fig. 2. Mock-up Messenger Chat for the Generative Conditions (Teaching-Only, Teaching + Drawing)

Note. The mock-up chat shows a message from the fictitious peer Mia, including a profile picture. Students in the teaching-only (left) and the teaching + drawing (right) could record a voice message. Translated from German.

4.4. Measures

Data collection was paper based. As this study was integrated within a larger research initiative, we only present the relevant variables for this study (see Appendix B, for detailed inventory of variables).

4.4.1. Conceptual knowledge

To evaluate students' conceptual knowledge in the pre-post-delayed test, we utilized the validated conceptual knowledge test ROC-CI by Wörner et al. (2022). The test consisted of 15 multiple-choice items, designed to test students' conceptual knowledge about the operation of a converging lens, including distractors which reflected common misconceptions (e.g., "The arrow travels as a whole to the lens, is flipped by the lens, and then travels to the screen"). For a correct answer, students were awarded two points, for a partly correct answer with one point, resulting in a maximum score of 30 points. To minimize the possibility of recognition bias, we displayed answer choices in a random sequence for the pre-, post-, and delayed test. Two independent raters coded 20 % of students' responses. The interrater reliability was excellent ($ICC_{2,1} = 1.00$), therefore only one of the raters coded the remaining answers. The reliability of the test was sufficient (McDonald's $\omega_t = 0.68$).

4.4.2. Monitoring accuracy

To evaluate students' monitoring accuracy, we asked them to predict their expected performance on the pretest, the immediate posttest, and the delayed posttest. Each of these predictions was made immediately before the corresponding test: "In the following you will answer 15 questions about the topic 'Imaging by converging lenses'. You can get

two points per question. In total, you can score 30 points. How many points do you think you will get?" (Baars et al., 2017; Jacob et al., 2022; Prinz et al., 2018) on a scale from zero to thirty points (for a similar approach, see Jacob et al., 2020, 2022; Schleinschok et al., 2017). We quantified monitoring accuracy for the pretest, immediate posttest, and delayed posttest through a bias metric³ (Lachner et al., 2020; Schraw, 2009), which measures the difference between the respective predicted and actual scores (i.e., $X_{\text{Judgment}} - X_{\text{Performance}}$). Negative values (minimum: -30) indicate students' underestimation, positive values (maximum: 30) indicate their overestimation, and a zero-value represents an exact accuracy. We used bias instead of, for example, absolute accuracy (which measures the precision of a single judgment by calculating the squared deviation from actual performance; Schraw, 2009) because bias is a more informative measure of the direction and magnitude of metacognitive judgment errors (for further methods to measure monitoring accuracy, see e.g., Fiorella et al., 2024; Fiorella & Jaeger, 2023; Fukaya, 2013; Schraw, 2009). In our case, bias provides additional explorative critical insights into over- or under-confidence, which could be essential for understanding metacognitive processes (Schraw, 2009).

³ In our preregistration, we mistakenly used the word 'absolute' when providing a detailed explanation of the bias measure for monitoring accuracy. We have disclosed this wording error to ensure transparency and scientific rigor. This approach aligns with the recommendations by Lakens (2024), who emphasizes that deviations from a preregistration due to errors can be transparently addressed to improve the validity of the analysis.

4.4.3. Academic self-concept in physics

We determined students' academic self-concept in physics with four items (e.g., "I even understand the most difficult tasks in physics lessons") on a four-point Likert scale from one "I completely disagree" to four "I completely agree" (see Flegr et al., 2023; Mang et al., 2018). Reliability was good (McDonald's $\omega_t = 0.81$).

4.4.4. Physics work ethic

Physics work ethic was operationalized as a facet of the personality trait conscientiousness (see De Fruyt et al., 2008; Mang et al., 2018; Roberts et al., 2014). We measured students' physics work ethic with four items (e.g., "I am paying attention in physics lessons") on a four-point Likert scale from one "I completely disagree" to four "I completely agree" (see Mang et al., 2018). Reliability was acceptable (McDonald's $\omega_t = 0.73$).

4.5. Procedure

The Ethics Committee of the University of Tübingen and the Ministry of Education and Cultural Affairs of the State of Baden-Württemberg approved this study. Participation was voluntary and data collection was limited to those students who had obtained written consent by their legal guardians. The procedure is summarized in Table 1.

Approximately one week before the teaching unit, the first author visited the schools to introduce the classes to the upcoming study. This visit also included administering the pretest (approx. 30 min) to evaluate the students' demographic information, prerequisites (e.g., academic self-concept in physics, physics work ethic), and their prior conceptual knowledge and monitoring accuracy.

One week later, the first author, who is also a certified and experienced physics teacher (10 years), conducted the main part of the study (henceforth mentioned as "teacher"). First, the students were introduced to the topic of the converging lens through a teacher-led presentation using visual slides and received the overview sheet (15 min). Afterwards, the students were randomly assigned to one of six conditions (after-study: restudy, teaching-only, teaching + drawing; distributed: restudy, teaching-only, teaching + drawing) within each class. Students in the after-study versus distributed condition were separated to the left and right side of the classroom with a classroom divider between.

After randomization, students in the after-study condition directly conducted the experiments (30 min) in small groups of usually four students. During this phase, communication between students and the teacher mirrored typical physics lessons, allowing students to seek help if they were struggling with a task. After reviewing the experimental results with their teacher to confirm their accurate documentation, these students either taught the contents to a fictitious peer or taught and drew a picture individually (15 min). Students in the after-study control condition restudied the contents in the same amount of time on their own (15 min). During this activity, each student was assigned a specific seat and equipped with sound-proof ear protectors to prevent disturbances from fellow students. All learning materials were available to the students during the task. This open-book format was employed to

circumvent any "hidden" retrieval-practice effects, and to keep the retrieval processes constant across conditions (Roelle et al., 2023; Sibley et al., 2022). Moreover, it has been demonstrated that open-book teaching can be more effective than closed-book teaching (Sibley et al., 2022).

After the randomization described above, students in the distributed conditions directly either taught the contents to a fictitious peer, taught and drew a picture, or restudied the contents individually (5 min). Subsequently, they started to conduct the first part of the experiments (hypotheses generation, 5 min) also in small groups of usually four students and then again either taught, taught and drew, or restudied the contents individually (5 min). Next, these students engaged in the next experimental phase with the same small group (25 min) and reviewed the experimental results with their teacher. Again, the students in the distributed conditions either taught, taught and drew, or restudied the contents on their own (5 min), which kept the total time on task constant across all conditions (in total 15 min).

Afterwards, all students answered the immediate posttest (approx. 20 min). Importantly, students' regular physics teachers were instructed not to further address the concept of the converging lens and its images during the following eight weeks. At the end of this period, the delayed posttest was administered by the first author.

4.6. Analysis of students' experimentation worksheets

To ensure high implementation fidelity, we assessed whether all students fully and correctly completed their experimentation worksheet, which was adapted from Flegr et al. (2023). Full and correct completion was coded as 1 (yes), while incomplete or incorrect completion was coded as 0 (no). This evaluation ensured that all students had the same basis for the subsequent learning activity.

4.7. Analysis of students' explanations, drawings, and restudy notes

Students in the teaching conditions (i.e., teaching-only, teaching + drawing) taught the contents to the fictitious peer "Mia", and their explanations were analyzed for completeness, elaboration, and correctness to capture the underlying cognitive processes (for a similar approach, see Fiorella & Kuhlmann, 2020; Hoogerheide, Renkl, et al., 2019; Jacob et al., 2020, 2022). Restudy notes, along with students' drawings in the teaching + drawing condition, were also evaluated using these same indicators (see also Ainsworth & Scheiter, 2021; Fiorella & Kuhlmann, 2020; Schmidgall et al., 2019; Schwamborn et al., 2010). For students in the distributed conditions, completeness, elaboration, and correctness were assessed based on the aggregated final product across all learning activity segments to provide a comprehensive analysis (for a similar approach, see Fiorella, 2022). The detailed analysis scheme for students' explanations, drawings, and restudy notes is available here: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/UK9CH>.

4.7.1. Completeness of students' explanations, drawings, and restudy notes

The completeness of students' outputs was coded by identifying the

Table 1
Procedure of the Study.

After-Study Conditions	Distributed Conditions
	Pretest (approx. 1 week before the Teaching Unit)
	The Teaching Unit: Introduction (15 min)
The Teaching Unit: Students' Experiments (30 min)	Learning Activity (5 min)
	The Teaching Unit: Students' Experiments (5 min)
Learning Activity (15 min)	Learning Activity (5 min)
	The Teaching Unit: Students' Experiments (25 min)
	Learning Activity (5 min)
	Immediate Posttest
	Delayed Posttest (after approx. 8 weeks)

Note. Bold items varied across experimental conditions (i.e., restudy, teaching-only, teaching + drawing).

concepts necessary to convey the learning contents: in the explanations and restudy notes, the concepts mentioned were coded; in the drawings, the concepts visually represented. Students could receive up to five points for each of the two task components (see Fig. 2), resulting in a maximum of ten points in total (explanations and restudy notes: e.g., one point for "The image is swapped left-right and top-bottom compared to the object"; drawings: e.g., one point for depicting a complete image on the screen despite a partially covered lens; self-developed coding scheme based on conceptual knowledge of the converging lens, see Wörner et al., 2022).

Independent raters coded 20 % of the explanations, drawings, and restudy notes. Interrater reliabilities were excellent (first part of the task: $ICC_{2,1} = 0.98-0.99$, second part: $ICC_{2,1} = 0.99-1.00$), so the remaining outputs (i.e., explanations, drawings, restudy notes) were split equally among the raters. The completeness scores from the two parts of the task were each added together, and this total value for completeness was used for further analysis of each teaching, drawing, or restudy note.

4.7.2. Elaboration of students' explanations, drawings, and restudy notes

We counted the number of elaborations in each explanation, drawing, and restudy note to assess the level of elaboration. This included idea units such as analogies, examples, and personal experiences (see also Fiorella & Kuhlmann, 2020; Jacob et al., 2020; Lachner et al., 2018). For instance, the statement, "If I cover the lens ring-shaped, the image on the screen is also simply less bright than before", qualifies as an elaboration because it introduces information not presented during the learning phase. Similarly, a drawn light ray tracing the path from a specific object point of the "L" through the converging lens to its corresponding image point is considered an elaboration, as this detail was also not provided during the learning phase.

Independent raters assessed the number of elaborations for 20 % of the explanations, drawings, and restudy notes. Interrater reliabilities were excellent for both parts of each task (first part: $ICC_{2,1} = 0.98-1.00$, second part: $ICC_{2,1} = 0.96-1.00$). Thus, the remaining outputs were evenly split among the raters for coding. A total score for the number of elaborations per explanation, drawing, or restudy note was then calculated and used for further analysis.

4.7.3. Correctness of students' explanations, drawings, and restudy notes

As an indicator of the level of correctness, we evaluated the percentage of correct knowledge reflected in the explanations, drawings, and restudy notes (Hoogerheide, Renkl, et al., 2019). First, we counted the idea units in both parts of each task. For example, in an explanation or restudy note, an idea unit was the statement "The image is less bright than before"; in a drawing, a drawn upside-down image of the "L". Next, we coded the number of physically correct idea units. Finally, we calculated the percentage of correct idea units for each part of the respective task.

Independent raters assessed the percentage of correct idea units for 20 % of students' outputs. Interrater reliabilities were excellent for both parts of the respective task (first part: $ICC_{2,1} = 0.94-1.00$, second part: $ICC_{2,1} = 0.96-1.00$). The remaining outputs were then evenly divided among the raters for coding. A total score for the percentage of correct idea units was calculated for each explanation, drawing, and restudy note and used for further analysis.

4.8. Data analyses

To test our preregistered hypotheses, we used planned contrasts while controlling students' prior conceptual knowledge or prior monitoring accuracy (Table 2). Conducting our preregistered contrast analyses instead of ANCOVAs allowed us to precisely test our hypotheses and their specific patterns (e.g., cascaded trends) while reducing the risk of alpha-inflation, as only one test was required (Furr & Rosenthal, 2003; Rosenthal & Rosnow, 1985). Moreover, contrast analyses are particularly recommended when testing specific hypotheses that cannot

be adequately addressed by conventional ANOVAs (e.g., main effects and interactions), such as cascaded or synergistic trends (Wiens & Nilsson, 2017) and also require smaller sample sizes compared to conventional ANOVAs. To address the hierarchical structure of the data, with students nested within classes and classes nested within schools, we applied multilevel modeling⁴ and incorporated cluster-robust standard errors. In the first contrast, we tested whether generation was more effective than restudy (i.e., restudy: -2; teaching-only: 1; teaching + drawing: 1). In the second contrast, we examined whether combining non-interactive teaching with drawing (i.e., teaching + drawing) was more beneficial than teaching-only (i.e., restudy: 0; teaching-only: -1; teaching + drawing: 1). Finally, in the third contrast, we tested whether the distributed learning activities were more effective than the after-study learning activities (i.e., after-study: -1; distributed: 1).

We explored potential interactions between the contrasted learning activities (i.e., restudy, teaching-only, teaching + drawing) and the timing factor (i.e., after-study, distributed) using the same planned contrast analyses conducted for the main effects. This approach allowed us to examine both main effects and interactions without the risk of alpha inflation associated with running multiple tests (Furr & Rosenthal, 2003; Rosenthal & Rosnow, 1985; Wiens & Nilsson, 2017). We also performed mediation analyses to explore potential mediation effects of the characteristics of students' explanations and restudy notes, using the contrast-coded experimental conditions as the independent variable. Additionally, we computed moderation analyses with the contrast coded predictors to test potential moderation effects of prior knowledge, academic self-concept, and work ethic.

As our field study comprised several measurement time points, missing values naturally occurred. In the preliminary and main analyses, the missing values were managed by applying multiple imputations across 50 datasets and 50 iterations.

Data were analyzed using R, version 4.4.1 (R Core Team, 2024).

5. Results

The preregistration, data, analyses, and supplementary material are available here: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/UK9CH>.

Cohen's d , partial η_p^2 , and ϕ were employed to measure effect sizes (small effects: $d = 0.20$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.01$, $\phi = 0.10$; medium effects: $d = 0.50$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.06$, $\phi = 0.30$; large effects: $d = 0.80$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.14$, $\phi = 0.50$, see Cohen, 2013). The alpha level was set to $\alpha = 0.05$.

5.1. Preliminary analysis

Our examination for potential outliers through boxplot visualization did not reveal any outliers. Further preliminary analyses showed no significant prior differences between the conditions concerning gender, $\chi^2(10, 317) = 6.83$, $p = .732$, $\phi = 0.14$, and first language, $\chi^2(10, 317) = 8.71$, $p = .563$, $\phi = 0.17$. Separate one-way ANOVAs across the six conditions (restudy after-study, restudy distributed, teaching-only after-study, teaching-only distributed, teaching + drawing after-study, teaching + drawing distributed) indicated that conditions did not differ in students' age, physics work ethic, academic self-concept in physics, prior conceptual knowledge, and prior monitoring accuracy, $.670 \leq p \leq .797$. Table 2 shows the mean scores and standard deviations per condition. Additionally, our implementation fidelity check confirmed that all 317 students fully and correctly completed the experimentation worksheet. As a further implementation check, comparisons between the characteristics of the restudy notes and the

⁴ Including an additional level for student group did not change the results; the outcomes remained stable. Therefore, we chose a multilevel model with the levels class and school to provide a more ecologically valid analysis (see Greenland, 2000; Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002).

Table 2
Means and Standard Deviations for all Measurements Across Experimental Conditions.

Variable	After-Study						Distributed					
	Restudy		Teaching-Only		Teaching + Drawing		Restudy		Teaching-Only		Teaching + Drawing	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Students' prerequisites												
Physics work ethic (1–4)	2.93	0.49	2.98	0.44	3.02	0.57	3.02	0.56	2.87	0.53	2.93	0.44
Academic self-concept in physics (1–4)	2.73	0.53	2.83	0.48	2.84	0.59	2.71	0.54	2.60	0.65	2.77	0.58
Prior												
Conceptual knowledge (0–30)	7.28	3.12	7.58	3.64	7.35	3.35	7.85	3.28	8.55	4.19	7.75	3.27
Monitoring accuracy ^a (–30–30)	9.94	6.95	9.94	6.37	9.84	6.94	9.93	6.88	8.06	7.31	8.83	5.30
Characteristics of students' explanations and restudy notes												
Completeness (0–10 points)	3.10	2.37	4.86	2.71	5.08	2.94	3.50	2.07	5.10	2.42	4.40	2.76
Elaboration (each 1 point)	2.12	2.50	3.42	3.33	3.60	7.53	2.67	2.12	3.70	3.67	4.98	6.02
Correctness (percentage)	94.84	9.78	91.98	13.13	94.04	9.16	89.58	14.15	79.58	19.88	90.61	10.77
Characteristics of students' drawings												
Completeness (0–10 points)	—	—	—	—	6.32	2.42	—	—	—	—	5.49	2.89
Elaboration (each 1 point)	—	—	—	—	1.96	2.77	—	—	—	—	2.65	3.35
Correctness (percentage)	—	—	—	—	87.13	19.35	—	—	—	—	77.37	23.74
Immediate												
Conceptual knowledge (0–30)	13.94	4.92	16.54	5.65	17.77	5.06	15.42	5.11	15.48	4.95	16.04	5.43
Monitoring accuracy ^a (–30–30)	2.08	7.94	–0.92	7.73	–1.92	6.94	0.44	6.83	–0.54	7.21	–1.09	7.66
Lasting												
Conceptual knowledge (0–30)	10.74	3.87	12.21	4.36	13.20	4.59	11.61	4.65	11.59	4.95	12.47	5.48
Monitoring accuracy ^a (–30–30)	2.69	6.16	0.00	6.92	0.14	7.07	2.50	6.89	1.69	7.73	1.04	6.61

Note. The data in this table are based on the raw data.

^a Monitoring accuracy is calculated based on the differences between students' estimated and actual performance. Negative values indicate underestimation, positive values overestimation, and a value of zero a perfect judgment of learning.

generated explanations, with regard to completeness, elaboration, and correctness, showed that the explanations were more complete ($\beta = 0.20, p < .001$, small effect), contained more elaborations ($\beta = 0.11, p < .001$, small effect), but had no higher proportion of correct idea units ($\beta = -0.05, p = .195$) than the restudy notes. The addition of drawing to the teaching component did not result in significant differences regarding completeness ($\beta = -0.04, p = .558$) and elaboration ($\beta = 0.08, p = .307$), but did in correctness ($\beta = 0.22, p = .001$, small effect). Similarly, the timing did not affect the level of completeness ($\beta = 0.00, p = .953$) and elaboration ($\beta = 0.08, p = .148$), but did affect correctness ($\beta = -0.22, p < .001$, small effect), see also Table 2.

5.2. Conceptual knowledge

In line with our generation hypothesis (H1a), contrast analysis concerning the immediate posttest showed that students who engaged in non-interactive teaching (i.e., teaching-only, teaching + drawing) had higher conceptual knowledge than students who restudied the contents ($\beta = 0.11, p = .005$, small effect; see Appendix C for detailed results). To explore whether cognitive mechanisms underlie this significant generation effect contrasted to restudy, we performed explorative separate

mediation analyses. The learning activity served as the predictor (generation contrast: $-2 =$ restudy, $1 =$ teaching-only, $1 =$ teaching + drawing), with completeness, elaboration, and correctness acting as individual mediators, and students' immediate conceptual knowledge as dependant variable. The analysis revealed a significant indirect effect through completeness, $a_1 \times b_1 = 0.15, p = .001$ (see Fig. 3 for the full mediation model). Neither elaboration nor correctness were significant mediators (for detailed results, see Appendix D).

The further contrasts were not significant, neither for immediate nor for lasting conceptual knowledge (see Appendix C for detailed results). This finding indicates that non-interactive teaching contributed to immediate learning but not to lasting learning. Additionally, neither drawing nor distributing generative activities contributed to students' conceptual knowledge.

In a next step, we also explored potential interactions between the contrasted learning activities (i.e., restudy, teaching-only, teaching + drawing) and the timing factor (i.e., after-study, distributed) using the same planned contrast analyses conducted for the main effects. In terms of immediate conceptual knowledge, we found a significant interaction between the contrasted restudy and generative conditions and timing ($\beta = -0.09, p = .017$, small effect; see Appendix C for further details). To

Fig. 3. Explorative Mediation Analysis in Terms of the Level of Completeness
Note. * $p < .050$. Regression coefficients are standardized.

break up this significant interaction, we conducted simple effect analyses regarding immediate conceptual knowledge. Results revealed that students who taught the learning contents only once (after the study phase) significantly outperformed students who taught distributed ($\beta = -0.30, p = .026$, small effect; after-study teaching: $M = 17.15, SD = 5.37$; distributed teaching: $M = 15.76, SD = 5.18$). In contrast, there was no effect of timing when students restudied the learning contents ($\beta = 0.25, p = .175$; after-study restudying: $M = 13.94, SD = 4.92$; distributed restudying: $M = 15.42, SD = 5.11$). Together, the results suggest that teaching had an effect on immediate conceptual knowledge only when teaching was conducted after-study.

5.3. Monitoring accuracy

Regarding immediate monitoring accuracy, there was a significant difference between the restudy condition and the generative conditions (i.e., teaching-only, teaching + drawing), $\beta = -0.09, p = .013$ (small effect). Based on the descriptive values, students in the restudy condition overestimated their knowledge ($M = 1.29, SD = 7.44$), however, a one-sample *t*-test showed that their judgments did not significantly differ from zero, $t(100) = 1.72, p = .090$. In contrast, students in the generative conditions underestimated their knowledge ($M = -1.11, SD = 7.36$), with a one-sample *t*-test indicating a significant difference from zero, $t(215) = -2.21, p = .029$.

None of the other contrasts were significant, neither for immediate nor for lasting monitoring accuracy (see Appendix C for detailed results).

5.4. Explorative analyses on students' individual differences

Given that our intervention demonstrated effects predominantly regarding immediate conceptual knowledge, we explored students' prior knowledge, academic self-concept, and work ethic as moderators of our learning activities in the immediate posttest. To ensure a comprehensive understanding, we also conducted the corresponding analyses regarding lasting conceptual knowledge. We utilized separate analyses, since running one analysis including correlated concepts could result in lower statistical power, unstable regression coefficients, and larger error terms (Aguinis, 1995). For detailed results see Appendix E (for correlations see Appendix F).

5.4.1. Prior knowledge

For immediate conceptual knowledge, we did not find a statistically significant interaction between students' prior knowledge and generation ($\beta = -0.04, p = .404$), nor between prior knowledge and drawing ($\beta = 0.02, p = .742$), nor between prior knowledge and distribution ($\beta = 0.07, p = .299$), nor between prior knowledge, generation, and distribution ($\beta = 0.04, p = .345$), and nor between prior knowledge, drawing, and distribution ($\beta = 0.04, p = .577$). None of the interactions for lasting conceptual knowledge were statistically significant.

5.4.2. Academic self-concept

For immediate conceptual knowledge, results revealed no significant interaction effects between students' academic self-concept and generation ($\beta = 0.02, p = .621$), not between academic self-concept and drawing ($\beta = 0.03, p = .726$), and not between academic self-concept and distribution ($\beta = -0.01, p = .859$). Interestingly, there was a statistically significant interaction between academic self-concept, generation, and distribution ($\beta = -0.08, p = .026$, small effect). To examine this interaction effect in more detail, we applied the Johnson-Neyman technique (Hayes & Montoya, 2017) which allows us to detect the significant range of students' academic self-concept in which the interaction is still significant. For the after-study condition, results revealed that students significantly benefited more from the generative activities than from restudying, however, only when their academic self-concept was medium to high (> -0.50). For students with a low academic

self-concept (≤ -0.50), there was no difference among conditions. For the distributed condition, students' academic self-concept did not moderate the learning effect. Thus, academic self-concept was only a determining factor when students only taught once after the study phase (see Fig. 4).

There was no statistically significant interaction between academic self-concept, drawing, and distribution ($\beta = 0.02, p = .780$). None of the interactions for lasting conceptual knowledge were statistically significant.

5.4.3. Physics work ethic

We did not find a statistically significant interaction effect of students' work ethic and generation ($\beta = 0.03, p = .371$), and not regarding work ethic and drawing ($\beta = 0.13, p = .066$) or work ethic and distribution ($\beta = 0.00, p = .952$). Again, there was a statistically significant interaction between work ethic, generation, and distribution ($\beta = -0.10, p = .009$, small effect). Regarding the after-study condition, the Johnson-Neyman technique revealed that for students with a physics work ethic of higher than -0.51 , the generative activities were significantly better than restudying, whereas there was no significant difference among conditions for students with a work ethic of exactly and lower than -0.51 . Regarding the distributed condition, there was no statistically significant interaction effect, indicating that students' work ethic only moderated after-study teaching (see Fig. 5).

There was no statistically significant interaction between work ethic, drawing, and distribution ($\beta = -0.07, p = .359$). None of the interactions for lasting conceptual knowledge were statistically significant.

6. Discussion

In this field experiment, we investigated whether the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching can be improved by a) incorporating drawing and b) distributing non-interactive teaching across the study phase with regard to students' conceptual knowledge and monitoring accuracy. Additionally, we examined cognitive (i.e., prior knowledge), motivational (i.e., academic self-concept), and personality (i.e., work ethic) factors as moderators of non-interactive teaching.

For immediate conceptual knowledge, in line with our generation hypothesis (H1a), we found that students who engaged in non-interactive teaching outperformed those who restudied the contents, mediated by the level of completeness. Contrary to our drawing hypothesis (H2a), however, drawing did not significantly contribute to the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching. That said, we did not find a main effect of distributing the non-interactive teaching activities (H3a). However, explorative analyses of potential interactions between non-interactive teaching and distributing suggested that teaching had an effect only when conducted after-study but not when distributed throughout the teaching unit. Our explorative analyses on students' individual differences showed that academic self-concept in physics and physics work ethic were associated with students' immediate conceptual knowledge. In the after-study conditions, students with higher levels of academic self-concept or work ethic benefited more from the generative conditions compared to restudying. In contrast, no moderating effects were observed for students with lower levels of academic self-concept or work ethic. Thus, academic self-concept and work ethic were only associated factors when teaching occurred after the study phase. We did not observe significant lasting conceptual knowledge effects. For immediate monitoring accuracy, students in the restudy condition numerically overestimated their knowledge, while those in the generative conditions (teaching-only, teaching + drawing) significantly underestimated their performance. None of the other effects were significant, including those related to lasting monitoring accuracy.

From a theoretical perspective, our findings add to the scarce evidence that non-interactive teaching is a beneficial learning strategy in the context of inquiry learning in schools (e.g., Fiorella & Mayer, 2014; Hoogerheide, Renkl, et al., 2019; Kobayashi, 2024; Lachner et al., 2021;

Fig. 4. Johnson-Neyman Confidence Intervals for Academic Self-Concept Moderation of Immediate Conceptual Knowledge in After-Study and Distributed Conditions. *Note.* The band reflects the 95 % confidence interval which can be used to demonstrate significant regions. Significant regions are highlighted in blue, non-significant regions in red. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Johnson-Neyman Confidence Intervals for Physics Work Ethic Moderation of Immediate Conceptual Knowledge in After-Study and Distributed Conditions. *Note.* The band reflects the 95 % confidence interval which can be used to demonstrate significant regions. Significant regions are highlighted in blue, non-significant regions in red. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Palinscar & Brown, 1984). However, adding drawing to non-interactive teaching did not enhance students' understanding of the learning contents. At first glance, this result seems to contrast with the recent study by Fiorella and Kuhlmann (2020). However, Fiorella and Kuhlmann (2020) conducted their study in a laboratory setting with adults and informed them about the general task of the subsequent learning activity even before the study phase (i.e., teaching expectancy).

Further, distributing non-interactive teaching during the study phase was not more beneficial than teaching only once after studying. This finding contradicts our hypothesis and prior research which showed that distributing non-interactive teaching enhanced students' understanding (Lachner et al., 2020). However, in the study by Lachner et al. (2020), the authors implemented a distributed non-interactive teaching task only once, namely in the middle of the study phase. In contrast, we implemented three distributed teaching tasks during the study phase. Thus, our study extends prior research as our results indicate that enhancing non-interactive teaching through distribution at multiple points during the study phase did not optimize school students' learning. Nevertheless, it is unclear why teaching once (in the middle of the study

phase) led to better outcomes but teaching several times during the study phase did not. One possible explanation is that frequent task-switching—between the respective learning activity and the ongoing teaching unit—may not always be beneficial. While one might assume that distributing learning activities benefits learning (Pan et al., 2024), it could also potentially increase the demands on students' working memory, particularly during knowledge construction. Future studies should investigate whether frequent interruptions in the learning process outweigh the benefits of distributed teaching and how to structure distribution in a way that optimally supports learning.

Interestingly, our analyses on students' individual differences revealed that prior knowledge did not moderate teaching and distributing as expected. Therefore, our findings are in line with other research that was unable to replicate such an interaction (Jacob et al., 2022; Richter et al., 2022). We attribute this finding to the fact that generative activities themselves are adaptable and can be worked on different levels of prior knowledge (Brod, 2024).

Additionally, our analyses revealed that academic self-concept moderated after-study learning activities regarding the acquisition of

immediate conceptual knowledge. Students with high academic self-concept appeared to benefit more from generative activities than from restudying. A strong academic self-concept likely enabled these students to approach the complex and challenging physics topic (Flegr et al., 2023; Wörner et al., 2022) with confidence, possibly facilitating generative processes essential for effective learning (Fiorella, 2023). In contrast, students with lower academic self-concept may have lacked the confidence or belief in their abilities to engage deeply with the task, reducing the effectiveness of teaching as a generative learning strategy. Notably, Jacob et al. (2022) found that students with low academic self-concept benefited more from teaching than retrieving. However, we want to note that Jacob et al. (2022) conducted their study in biology. Given that academic self-concept is domain-specific, our findings suggest that such ATI-effects may also depend on the particular domain in which non-interactive teaching is implemented (see also Sibley et al., 2024).

To our knowledge, we were the first to investigate the moderating role of physics work ethic regarding non-interactive teaching. Our findings demonstrated that work ethic, as a facet of conscientiousness, moderated after-study activities regarding immediate conceptual knowledge, which is also in line with previous publications in related areas (Bareis et al., 2024; Rieger et al., 2022; Song et al., 2020). We want to make explicit that we deliberately did not explore potential moderated mediations due to our restricted sample size and the fairly complex 3×2 -design.

6.1. Study limitations and future research

One limitation concerns the authenticity of our experimental field study. While our study was aligned with the physics curriculum and all lessons and study components were conducted personally by the first author (researcher and experienced physics teacher), the experimental setting may have dampened natural classroom dynamics, making it difficult to fully generalize the findings to real classroom teaching. Moreover, to isolate the lasting effects of the interventions, regular physics teachers were explicitly instructed not to revisit the topic of the converging lens and its images during the eight weeks between the immediate and delayed posttest. However, this differs from typical classroom practice, where topics are often periodically reinforced. Additionally, students may have independently engaged with the topic, introducing a potential confounding factor. Future research could enhance ecological validity by embedding interventions more seamlessly into standard classroom routines, thereby supporting the long-term integration of evidence-based teaching strategies. Additionally, we focused exclusively on physics. Given that prior research suggests non-interactive teaching is not equally effective across subjects or domains (Sibley et al., 2024) and that age-related differences exist (Brod, 2021), the generalizability of our findings remains uncertain.

Further limitations arise from the study design. First, while using the same conceptual knowledge test at three time points ensured consistency, it may have introduced recognition effects. To mitigate this, we randomized the order of answer options to prevent students from relying solely on memory. Nonetheless, future studies could explore alternative test formats to minimize potential biases. Second, we did not include a drawing-only condition, as our primary goal was to investigate whether adding drawing enhances the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching. Additionally, it would be valuable to replicate our findings under conditions where students are informed before studying that they will teach, as previous research suggests that this expectation can influence learning outcomes (Fiorella & Mayer, 2014; Guerrero & Wiley, 2021; Kobayashi, 2024).

It is also important to note that the observed effects were relatively modest, which may be attributed to the short duration of the intervention. Students engaged in generative tasks (i.e., teaching-only, teaching + drawing) only once for 15 min or in three separate five-minute segments. These brief intervals may not have provided sufficient time for

students to fully engage with the teaching experience as a generative activity. Although each five-minute segment began only after all students were ready, we cannot rule out that some students may have needed additional time to process the material, potentially reducing overall time-on-task. Moreover, a total exposure of 15 min across all conditions may not have been sufficient to foster lasting learning effects over an eight-week period. Nonetheless, we want to note that our obtained findings are consistent with prior meta-analytic evidence (e.g., Lachner et al., 2022; Ribosa & Duran, 2022).

7. Conclusion

Our results demonstrated that non-interactive teaching was an effective generative strategy for supporting students' learning in school, likely because it led to a higher level of completeness compared to restudying. However, incorporating drawing or distributing non-interactive teaching at several time points during the learning phase did not yield additional learning benefits. Moreover, our study highlights the need to consider non-cognitive learner characteristics, as they can shape the non-interactive teaching effect. These insights provide valuable directions for optimizing non-interactive teaching and highlight the importance of considering individual differences in educational practice.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Heike Russ: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Leonie Sibley:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Salome Flegr:** Resources, Conceptualization. **Jochen Kuhn:** Resources, Conceptualization. **Vincent Hoogerheide:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Katharina Scheiter:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Andreas Lachner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT-4o in order to ensure error-free spelling and to receive suggestions for more suitable phrasing. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

No competing interest.

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Appendix

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